

Variation of Cation Exchange and Selectivity Co-efficients of Trace Elements between Montmorillonite Clays and Resins with Concentration of the Dispersed Phase

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Exchange studies have been made between varying amounts of H-resin and varying concentrations of clays associated with trace elements nickel, cobalt, copper and zinc. Selectivity co-efficients have also been calculated from the exchange data at different clay concentrations.

The exchange of ions and selectivity co-efficients are found to decrease with the concentration of the clay suspension. The decrease is attributed to the overlapping of electrical double layer and subsequent immobilization of ions. The rate of decrease of ion exchange and selectivity co-efficients becomes less prominent as the clay concentration increases. This may be due to ion-hydration and subsequent prevention of electrical double layers.

The isotherms obtained with the varying amounts of hydrogen ions in H-resin are somewhat reversed in shape to ordinary adsorption isotherms and similar to those obtained by other ions.

Plants require different elements for their nutrition and growth. It is assumed that they absorb these ions from the soils by a process of ion-exchange. The conditions existing surrounding root-soil zone are really complicated. Many attempts have been made to study this exchange property of the clays by artificial ways. The procedure usually adopted for this purpose simulates little of the conditions obtaining in the plant root zone. For instance, the exchange of ions is usually studied in diluted systems and that too in the presence of perhaps foreign electrolytes at a concentration quite inconceivable in the root zone. The usual practice is to extrapolate or apply as it is, the information gained under the artificial conditions to the natural soil-root system. The electrolyte concentration being ordinarily small at the root-zone, Pallmann *et al*¹ and later on Mukherjee² suggested the use not of the symmetry value but of a P^c value to characterise the clays.

Brown and Albrecht³ and later on Chatterjee⁴ adopted a new method to study the exchange property of the soils by artificial means. Their method simulates almost soil-root system. It consists in having a H-system (clay or plant root) separated by a suitable membrane (colloidion or cellophane) from the soil colloid saturated with one or more kinds of ions. The membrane does not seem to interfere with the exchange. Moreover, the soil-root condition can easily be simulated. On the basis of their studies, Brown and Albrecht (*loc. cit*) and Chatterjee⁵ showed that ions on the clay surface differ in the ease

1. Pallmann, H *et al.*, *Annale Faculte d' Agronomie Bucares*, 1939-40 1.

2. S. K. Mukherjee, *Bull Ind. Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1951, 6.

3. D. A. Brown and Wm. A. Albrecht, *Res. Bull No. 477*, College of Agric. Univ. of MO. (1950)

4. A. Chatterjee, *J. Ind. Soc. Soil. Sci.*, 1954, Vol.-II.

5. A. Chatterjee, *Jour. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 34, 8.

with which they exchange with H-ions of the root system. Chatterjee (loc. cit) carried out the exchange experiments between H-resin and homo-ionic clays saturated with common ions usually found present in soils. In the present investigation the exchange characteristics of the trace elements present in soils are studied at different concentrations of the base saturated clays and their selectivity co-efficients are also calculated.

The selectivity co-efficients as defined by different workers^{6,7} are calculated by dividing the ratio of the concentrations raised to appropriate powers of the two ions involved in the exchange reaction in one phase to that in the other. Between uni-bivalent ions the equilibrium constants of the reversible exchange reactions may be represented as

$$2A^+ - Rd + B^{2+} - Md \rightleftharpoons B^{2+} - Rd + 2A^+ - M$$

$$\text{Or } A^+ - R + B^{2+} - M \rightleftharpoons B^{2+} - R + A^+ - M.$$

$$K_A^B = \frac{[A^+]_M^2 [B^{2+}]_R}{[A^+]_R^2 [B^{2+}]_M} = \frac{[B^{2+}]_R / [A^+]_R^2}{[B^{2+}]_M / [A^+]_M^2}$$

$$K_A^{1B} = \frac{[B^{2+}]_R^{1/2} [A^+]_M}{[A^+]_R [B^{2+}]_M^{1/2}} = \frac{[B^{2+}]_R^{1/2} / [A^+]_R}{[B^{2+}]_M^{1/2} / [A^+]_M} = \sqrt{K_A^B}$$

where the expressions in parenthesis denote concentrations and subscripts R and M denote the two solid exchanger phases viz., synthetic resin exchanger and montmorillonite clay respectively.

The distribution of trace element ions usually found present in the soil clays between montmorillonite clay and electrolytic solution was measured by Basu *et al* (loc. cit.) and the selectivity co-efficients were calculated. In the present investigation the complicating effects of complex formation is avoided, by selecting two solid exchangers, the resin phase simulating plant root and the montmorillonite clay saturated with trace element cations. The selectivity co-efficients will obviously depend on the relative abundance of the ions and their relative affinities towards the exchangers.

EXPERIMENTAL

The H-clay was prepared by following the usual method of electro dialysis of the clay fraction ($<2\mu$) isolated from a sample of Gujrat bentonite. The b.e.c of this clay fraction was determined by KCl-KOH method of Ganguly⁸ and was found to be 96.0 ± 0.2 meq/100 gms dry clay. The pH of 3.17% colloidal suspension was 3.67. Cu, Ni, Co and Zn-clays were prepared by leaching the H-clay at $p^H=3.67$ with 0.5(M) solution of $CuSO_4$, $NiSO_4$, $Co(NO_3)_2$ and $ZnSO_4$ solutions respectively. Usually the leaching was continued for 3-4 days. It was then washed free of the electrolytes by centrifuging it with as small an amount of acidulated water ($p^H=4$) as possible, in instalments till the leached water was free from electrolytes. This was necessary to prevent the hydrolysis of clay salts. The clay salts were then suspended in double distilled water in pyrex bottles.

6. C. E. Marshall and Garcia, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1959, **63**, 1663.

7. A. N. Basu, B. K. Seal, and S. K. Mukherjee, *Jour. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **39**, 71.

8. A. K. Ganguly, *J. Phys. and Coll. Chem.*, 1951, **55**, 1417.

Amberlite 120 resin was converted into the H-form by repeated treatment of the resin with HCl. It was washed free of the acid with distilled water and dried at 105°C. The b.e.c of the H-resin was then measured by suspending known amount of this resin in a known volume of standard alkali, shaken and then the alkali was back titrated with a standard acid. The b.e.c. was found to be 460 meq per 100 gms dry resin. The experimental procedure for the study of the exchange between the H-resin and base saturated clays at various concentrations was described by Chatterjee in earlier papers (loc. cit.).

The selectivity co-efficients $K_H^{M^{2+}}$ where M^{2+} denotes Co^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} are calculated from exchange data. The figures in the bracket are the equilibrium pH values of the clays.

TABLE I

Reaction between H-resin and Co-clay

Amount of resin corresponding to	Total $Co^{2+}=74$ meq/100 gms. dry clay		Total $Co^{2+}=73$ meq/100 gms dry clay		Total $Co^{2+}=73$ meq/100 gms dry clay		Total $Co^{2+}=74$ meq/100 gms dry clay	
	Strength=0.5% $pH=5.3$	Selectivity Co-efficient	Strength 1.2% $pH=5.6$	Selectivity Co-efficient	Strength=1.713% $pH=5.05$	Selectivity Co-efficient	Strength=5% $pH=4.14$	Selectivity Co-efficient
1. 0.5S	20.9 (4.04)	0.666	17.24(3.92)	0.216	16.94(4.14)	0.2113	15.00(3.76)	0.1196
2. 1.0S	22.8 (3.96)	0.088	18.00 (3.84)	0.0315	16.7 (3.8)	0.0249	16.3 (3.60)	0.0222
3. 1.5S	23.75 (3.84)	0.0623	21.2 (3.80)	0.0212	18.64(3.74)	0.0138	18.7(3.51)	0.01185
4. 2.0S	25.33 (3.80)	0.0055	23.95 (3.68)	0.0164	23.76 (3.6)	0.0174	22.00(3.42)	0.0128

TABLE II

Reaction between H-resin and Ni-clay

Amount of resin corresponding to	Total $Ni^{2+}=62$ meq/100 gms dry clay		Total $Ni^{2+}=62$ meq/100 gms dry clay		Total $Ni^{2+}=62$ meq/100 gms dry clay		Total $Ni^{2+}=63$ meq/100 gms dry clay	
	Strength 1%, $pH=4.9$	Selectivity Co-efficient	Strength=1.42%, $pH=4.23$	Selectivity Co-efficient	Strength 2.54%, $pH=4.06$	Selectivity Co-efficient	Strength=7.47% $pH=4.02$	Selectivity Co-efficient
1. 0.5S	26.15 (4.04)	2.094	18.65(3.58)	0.891	16.52 (3.12)	1.48×10^{-2}	15.00 (3.70)	5.4×10^{-3}
2. 1.0S	28.44 (3.9)	0.606	20.94(3.40)	0.123	18.38 (2.9)	0.72×10^{-2}	17.44 (3.10)	5.6×10^{-2}
3. 1.5S	31.45 (3.6)	0.269	22.61 (3.32)	0.055	21.8 (2.7)	0.75×10^{-2}	18.41 (2.90)	2.4×10^{-2}
4. 2.0S	36.27 (3.46)	0.2412	29.3 (3.20)	0.038	30.38 (2.56)	1.4×10^{-2}	23.14 (2.52)	3.9×10^{-2}

TABLE III

Reaction between H-resin and Cu-clay

Amount of resin corresponding to	Total Cu ²⁺ =62 meq/100 gms dry clay		Total Cu ²⁺ =62 meq/100 gms dry clay		Total Cu ²⁺ =63 meq/100 gms dry clay		Total Cu ²⁺ =63 meq/100 gms dry clay	
	Strength=0.92% pH=4.86	Strength=1.5% pH=4.47	Strength=3.3% pH=3.84	Strength=6.71% pH=4.3	Meq of H-ions replaced by Cu ²⁺ ions.	Selectivity co-efficient	Meq of H-ions replaced by Cu-ions.	Selectivity co-efficient
1. 0.5S	26.44 (3.03)	0.1298	21.28 (2.82)	0.0728	18.72 (2.9)	5.5×10 ⁻³	6.87 (3.68)	3.6×10 ⁻³
2. 1.0S	28.19 (2.91)	0.579	24.15 (2.80)	0.2594	20.00 (2.87)	7.9×10 ⁻²	8.96 (3.54)	4.5×10 ⁻³
3. 1.5S	29.54 (2.87)	0.023	24.69 (2.80)	0.0486	24.01 (2.78)	2.2×10 ⁻²	10.25 (3.44)	3.2×10 ⁻³
4. 2.0S	31.93 (2.82)	0.0215	25.58 (2.78)	0.0335	31.19 (2.76)	4.5×10 ⁻²	13.01 (3.40)	5.04×10 ⁻³

TABLE IV

Reaction between H-resin and Zn-clay

Amount of resin corresponding to	Total Zn ²⁺ =43.5 meq/100 gms dry clay		Total Zn ²⁺ =43.5 meq/100 gms dry clay		Total Zn ²⁺ =43.0 meq/100 gms dry clay		Total Zn ²⁺ =42.5 meq/100 gms dry clay	
	Strength=0.98% pH=4.02	Strength=2.2% pH=3.91	Strength=3.1% pH=3.5	Strength=7.6% pH=3.1	Meq of H-ions replaced by Zn-ions.	Selectivity co-efficient	Meq of H-ions replaced by Zn-ions.	Selectivity co-efficient
1. 0.5S	12.5 (3.41)	0.714	8.9 (3.2)	0.1223	2.62 (3.3)	1.19×10 ⁻³	2.28 (3.03)	5.9×10 ⁻⁴
2. 1.0S	15.1 (3.39)	0.1517	7.03 (3.14)	7.1×10 ⁻³	4.64 (3.16)	1.67×10 ⁻³	2.54 (2.96)	2.4×10 ⁻⁴
3. 1.5S	18.5 (3.31)	0.116	9.15 (3.05)	1.35×10 ⁻³	5.37 (3.06)	1.15×10 ⁻³	3.24 (2.76)	2.2×10 ⁻⁴
4. 2.0S	18.5 (3.17)	0.054	9.71 (3.01)	4.5×10 ⁻³	6.85(3.02)	1.37×10 ⁻³	3.4 (2.72)	1.4×10 ⁻⁴

DISCUSSION

The nature of variation of ion-exchange and selectivity co-efficient of the ions with the concentration of clay and also with the amount of H-resin i.e., the concentration of H⁺-ion in the resin phase are shown in the Figs. 1 and 2. The amount of H-resin have been expressed in terms of symmetry concentration in the tables.

The influence of concentration on the ease of replacement of the cations associated with the clay for the H⁺ ion of H-resin is clearly noticeable from Fig. 1(b).

In case of Co-clay the rate of exchange initially falls slowly as the clay concentration increases and then remains almost constant. Ni-clay also behaves in a similar way, the only difference is that in case of 2.0S, the rate of exchange shows an initial decrease followed by a slight increase and a final decrease.

The behaviour of Cu and Zn-clay is somewhat different. Here the rate of exchange decreases more sharply and this decrease is continued upto the clay concentration studied in case of Cu-clay while Zn-clay, at a higher concentration attains a, more or less, steady value. Like Na-clay system, Cu-clay with 2.0 symmetry concentrations of H-ion shows an initial decrease followed by a sharp rise and a final steady decrease in the rate of exchange.

FIG. 1

The decrease in the rate of exchange with the clay concentration may be attributed to the overlapping of the double layer and consequent ‘‘immobilization’’ of ions. The small decrease in the case of Co and Ni-clay systems may be due to the hydration of ions which are known to form co-ordinated compounds with water. The molecules of water of hydration associated with these ions prevent the overlapping of the double layers when the sol is concentrated and that results in small decrease in the rate of exchange.

FIG. 2

Section(a) of the Fig. 1 represents the amount of cation exchanged as a function of the symmetry concentration of H-ions in the hydrogen resin. The slopes of the isotherms of all the systems are similar to those of bivalent ions as measured earlier (loc. cit), the notable exceptions being those of 1.5% Cu-clay, 0.98% and 7.6% Zn clay where the slopes are somewhat reversed and are similar to those obtained with electrolytes.

The selectivity co-efficients when plotted against clay concentration in Fig. 2(b) also follow the same nature. The values decrease sharply with the increase of clay concentration upto some extent, then remains practically constant and the rate is greater at

9. A. Chatterjee and S. K. Mukherjee, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **43**, 11.

10. C. E. Marshall,—‘‘Physical Chemistry and Mineralogy of soils’’ vol. I. John Wiley and Sons, New York.

low symmetry concentrations of the resin⁹. The selectivity co-efficient values of Co, Cu and Zn-clays with the H-resin are, more or less, similar whereas those of Ni-clays are much higher. The decrease in selectivity co-efficients with increasing clay concentration may be traced to the same reason as that of the overlapping of double layers between two contiguous phases as the clay becomes concentrated and the horizontal portions in the curve may be due to the hydration effect of the ions.

Marshall¹⁰ has shown that the variation of mean bonding energy of different ions with the clay concentration is to be considered on the basis of the behaviour of the ion in the resultant electrical field as the two charged particles are brought nearer.

The higher values of the selectivity co-efficients at low concentrations are likely to be due to the increased dissociation of the ions which is reduced as the clay concentration increases resulting in higher free cation bonding energies and hence lower selectivity co-efficient values.

The selectivity co-efficient when plotted as a function of symmetry concentration of the H-ions in the H-resin [Sec(a) in Fig. 2] also shows the same nature of initial sharp decrease followed by a, more or less, constant value. Here also the selectivity co-efficient values are much higher with the lowest concentration of the clay used and that, too, when the symmetry concentration of H-ions in H-resin is small.

In case of Cu-clay the selectivity co-efficient values are found to be maximum when 1.0S symmetry concentration of H-ions in the H-resin are used.

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9. A. Chatterjee and S. K. Mukherjee, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 43, 11.
10. C. E. Marshall, "Physical Chemistry and Mineralogy of soils", vol. I. John Wiley and Sons, New York.